

Verification and Validation (VV) Plan for neutronic computing tools used for the design of newcleo's LFRs

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ABSTRACT

newcleo is currently designing two Lead-cooled Fast Reactor (LFR) cores: LFR-AS-30 and LFR-AS-200. This paper summarizes the Verification and Validation (V&V) Plan developed by *newcleo* for neutronics. The plan establishes a comprehensive framework for Verification, Validation, and Uncertainty Quantification (VVUQ) of neutronic models and scientific computing tools supporting the design and safety assessment of LFRs. It integrates deterministic and stochastic codes, a systematic validation strategy based on experiments, and uncertainty propagation methods aligned with recognized international standards. This summary outlines the methodology, experimental basis, data sources, and future perspectives of the V&V plan, within *newcleo*'s broader design and safety demonstration framework.

Keywords: Verification, Validation, Neutronics, Uncertainty Quantification

1. INTRODUCTION

The development of Generation IV lead-cooled fast reactors (LFRs) requires a rigorous verification and validation process for the scientific computing tools (SCTs) used in their design and safety demonstration. The V&V plan follows the methodology outlined in the reference documents [1, 2] and in the regulatory guidance from the Autorité de Sûreté Nucléaire et de Radioprotection (ASNR) [3]. The plan defines the variables of interest, the validation experiments, and the strategy for the validating each variable of interest within the domain of utilisation. Together with the definition of the methods for quantifying uncertainties, and the computational framework used to ensure reproducible and defensible safety analyses, the V&V plan constitutes the basis for the qualification of the neutronic SCTs.

2. METHODOLOGY AND COMPUTATIONAL FRAMEWORK

newcleo is designing two LFR cores; these are LFR-AS-30 (30 MWe) and LFR-AS-200 (200 MWe). Their main characteristics are presented in Table I, where the Pu quality is defined as the ratio between the sum of Pu-239 and Pu-241 atoms and the sum of all atoms in the Pu vector. A crosscut of the LFR-AS-200 and LFR-AS-30 cores are presented in Figures 2 and 1, respectively.

The VVUQ approach uses both deterministic and Monte Carlo simulations to obtain best-estimate neutronic parameters with quantified uncertainties. The main SCTs employed include ERANOS-2.3N [4], DRAGON5/DONJON [5], Serpent-2 [6], OpenMC-0.15 [7], and MCNP-6.3 [8]. Nuclear data are processed using NJOY2016 [9] and CALENDF-2010 [10] for a given nuclear data evaluation. Uncertainties arise from nuclear data, modelling approximations, and computational methods. These contributions are combined quadratically and validated against integral experimental benchmarks. The plan follows a Best Estimate Plus Uncertainty (BEPU) approach, ensuring that all safety-relevant parameters are supported by experimental evidence.

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Table I. Main design parameters of the LFR-AS-30 and LFR-AS-200 cores.

Design Quantity	LFR-AS-30	LFR-AS-200
Fuel type / Pu content	MOX (U+Pu) 25–35 wt.%Pu	MOX (U+Pu) 15–25 wt.%Pu
Pu quality	≈ 60 at.%	≈ 60 at.%
Active zone radius / height	≈ 80cm/70cm	≈ 150cm/90cm

Figure 1. Crosscut of the LFR-AS-30

Figure 2. Crosscut of the LFR-AS-200

3. EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION STRATEGY

3.1. Identification of relevant experiments

The V&V plan identifies a set of experiments relevant to fast-spectrum systems. This selection is based on criteria such as the representativeness of the experiments with respect to reference reactor cores. Due to the limited availability of lead-cooled experiments, the plan also includes Sodium Fast Reactor (SFR) experiments where sensitivity analyses demonstrate comparable neutron physics. As an example, in Figure 3 and Figure 4, sensitivity profiles of k_{eff} with respect to variations of Pu-239 fission and U-238 capture cross section are compared between BERENICE – ZONA 2 (SFR) and the *newcleo*'s LFRs cores. Experiments come from databases such as the International Criticality Safety Benchmark Evaluation Project (ICSBEP) [11] and the International Reactor Physics Handbook (IRPhE) [12]. Key experiments include Los Alamos spheres (e.g., GODIVA, JEZEBEL, HMF27, PMF35), BFS-61, BERENICE, SNEAK 7A/7B, ZPPR, ZPR, SEFOR, FCA-IX and JOYO MK-II.

Figure 3. Sensitivity of k_{eff} to Pu-239 fission cross section, ECCO-33 energy structure, computed using ERANOS-2.3N and the ENDF/B-VIII.0 library.

Figure 4. Sensitivity of k_{eff} to U-238 capture cross section, ECCO-33 energy structure, computed using ERANOS-2.3N and the ENDF/B-VIII.0 library.

3.2. The Validation Matrices

The main outcome of the selection of experiments consists in the draft of validation matrices. These matrices are constructed for each core characteristic, covering reactivity, neutron spectra, flux and power distributions, control rod worth, reactivity feedback, kinetic parameters, mass balance and burnup. Validation matrices ensure traceability between experiments and the core characteristics, or variables of interest. A selection of experiments for verification and validation purposes of *newcleo* cores is summarized in Table II. The Los Alamos spheres in the selection, which are characterized by different fuel compositions (either enriched U or Pu) and reflectors (made of uranium, lead, or absent), could provide information on the reflector gain and the cross sections for different heavy metal isotopes. Preliminary sensitivity studies demonstrate that LFR and SFR systems have similar neutronic responses for key isotopes such as Pu-239 fission and U-238 capture, as can be seen in Figures 3 and 4. This supports the inclusion of SFR benchmarks in the validation database. Among these, the BERENICE and SNEAK have a similar fuel composition with respect to *newcleo* cores, demonstrate good representativeness

and have precise measurements of kinetic parameters. The SEFOR experiments offer valuable insights on the Doppler coefficient. ZPPR and ZPR have been selected because they use slightly different fuels, which could provide further information on cross sections of Pu isotopes and other variables of interest. BFS-61 experiment is particularly valuable due to its use of lead as a coolant and reflector, providing direct insight of neutron reflection and spectral effects characteristic of LFR cores. Finally, measurements of reaction rates in FCA-IX and of fuel cycle-related parameters in JOYO KM-II will enable uncertainties of mass balance over burnup to be quantified. Since uncertainties on neutronic parameters arise primarily from nuclear data (cross sections, resonance parameters), nuclear data covariance data are used to estimate propagated uncertainties via sensitivity analysis and select the appropriate experiments.

3.3. Uncertainty Quantification and Representativity

The LFR reactors of *newcleo* have a novel design, requiring R&D activities. The designer will have to perform all the required actions to derive BEPU core characteristics for LFR-AS-30 and LFR-AS-200, to be validated through experiments. Let R_R be a variable of interest, e.g. the reactivity, to be assessed in the reactor, in a given configuration of interest for the nuclear safety case. The dispersion ΔR_R due to nuclear data (computational method uncertainties can be neglected when using Monte Carlo calculations) of the variable of interest R_R , is computed as

$$\Delta R_R = \sqrt{S_R^T D S_R}, \quad (1)$$

where S_R is the sensitivity of the variable of interest R_R to nuclear data variations and D is the nuclear data relative covariance matrix. Given an integral experiment E , the dispersion ΔR_E due to nuclear data (again neglecting method uncertainty) of the same variable of interest R_E is estimated by:

$$\Delta R_E = \sqrt{S_E^T D S_E}, \quad (2)$$

where S_E is the sensitivity of R_E to nuclear data variations. The representativity factor r_{RE} quantifies how closely the sensitivity profiles of the reactor and the experiment align considering the uncertainties of the associated response. A value close to one indicates that the experiment is highly representative of the reactor's neutron physics and thus more valuable for validation purposes. The representativity factor is defined as [1]:

$$r_{RE} = \frac{S_R^T D S_E}{\sqrt{S_R^T D S_R} \sqrt{S_E^T D S_E}}. \quad (3)$$

For example, as the sensitivity profiles of BERENICE-ZONA2 and *newcleo*'s cores are similar, the representativity factors for BERENICE-ZONA2 with respect to LFR-AS-30 are 0.767 and 0.813 for k_{eff} and β_{eff} , respectively. This indicates a strong correlation. Such correlations inform the prioritization of future experimental programs. For an experiment E to be accepted, the uncertainty of its measurements Δb_E must be smaller than the uncertainty due to nuclear data R_E . A value of the so-called weight parameter

$$w_E = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{\Delta b_E^2}{\Delta R_E^2}}, \quad (4)$$

close to one indicate that the experiment provides meaningful and reliable information for validation. In the experimental assimilation, Bayes' theorem is employed to reduce the uncertainty ΔR_R using the data from the experiment. Specifically, it consists in the assessment of the *a posteriori* uncertainty ΔR_R^* to be applied to the estimation of R_R through relation

$$\Delta R_R^* = \Delta R_R \sqrt{1 - \frac{r_{RE}^2}{1 + \frac{\Delta b_E^2}{\Delta R_E^2}}}. \quad (5)$$

Experiments	Reactivity	Neutron spectrum	Neutron flux spatial distribution	Power per fuel assembly and linear power	Control Rods worth	Reactivity Feedback effects	Kinetic parameters	Mass balance	Burnup
HFM28	×								
PMF36	×								
MMF58	×								
JEMIMA	×								
BIGTEN	×								
FLATTOP U-235	×								
GODIVA	×						×		
JEZEBEL Pu-239	×						×		
JEZEBEL Pu-240	×								
BFS61	×	×	×						
BERENICE R2	×	×	×				×		
BERENICE ZONA2	×	×	×				×		
SNEAK 7A	×	×	×				×		
SNEAK 7B	×	×	×				×		
ZPPR-2	×	×	×			×			
ZPPR-10A	×	×	×		×	×			
ZPR-6A7	×								
ZPR-6A7-2	×								
SEFOR-1	×					×			
SEFOR-2	×					×			
JOYO MK-II	×			×	×			×	×
FCA-IX	×	×							

Table II. List of experiments for variables of interest.

The reduction of uncertainty is maximum if both the representativity factor r_{RE} and the weight parameter are close to unity, which is achieved when sensitivities of experiment and reactor parameter are similar and the experimental uncertainty Δb_E is small. Uncertainty reduction can also be achieved by employing multiple consistent experiments. Figure 5 shows the reduction of uncertainty $\Delta R_R^*/\Delta R_R$ as a function of the ratio $\Delta b_E/\Delta R_E$, for different representativity factors r_{RE} . If the uncertainty ΔR_R^* is larger than that required by the designer, and representative experiments of the design are available, the assimilation of these experimental data is also possible.

Figure 5. Reduction of uncertainty as a function of the ratio of experimental uncertainty and its associated dispersion for different representativity factors.

3.4. Integral Data Assimilation

Once relevant experiments have been identified, there is a need to combine all this information in a single process. This is customarily performed by relying on the information theory, also known as Integral Data Assimilation or Nuclear Data Adjustment and Transposition Method [2]. Bayesian formalism provides a natural framework for combining prior information on nuclear data with observations from integral experiments. The prior distribution represents the evaluated nuclear data and their associated covariance matrices. The posterior distribution represents the updated nuclear data, and associated covariance matrices, after assimilating experimental results. Let us denote:

- x the vector of nuclear data parameters, e.g. multigroup cross sections.
- y : the vector of integral experimental observables, e.g. k_{eff} , reaction rate ratios.
- S : sensitivity matrix linking changes in nuclear data to variations in all the selected observables.
- D_x : prior covariance matrix of nuclear data uncertainties.
- D_y : covariance matrix of experimental uncertainties which would be identical to Δb_E for a single experiment.

The relationship between the nominal observables y_0 calculated using the prior data set x_0 , and the experimental observables y_E is approximated by a linear perturbation model. It is assumed that any set of observables y , calculated with a posterior set of data x , can be described as

$$y = y_0 + S(x - x_0), \quad (6)$$

provided that the difference between x and x_0 is small enough. The assimilation process aims to find the posterior mean x^* and covariance D_x^* that minimize the discrepancy between the calculated set y and experiment y_E . Using Bayes' theorem under the assumption of Gaussian distributions for both prior and experimental uncertainties, the posterior mean and covariance are given by the classical Kalman

filter form [2]:

$$\begin{aligned} x^* &= x_0 + D_x S^\top \left(S D_x S^\top + D_y \right)^{-1} (y_E - y_0), \\ D_x^* &= D_x - D_x S^\top \left(S D_x S^\top + D_y \right)^{-1} S D_x. \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

The posterior mean x^* corresponds to the most probable nuclear data vector, and the posterior covariance D_x^* quantifies the reduced uncertainty after assimilation. The matrix term $K = D_x S^\top (S D_x S^\top + D_y)^{-1}$ is often referred to as the 'gain matrix', determining the weighting between prior information and experimental evidence. Integral Data Assimilation can be employed to reduce the uncertainties on key variables of interests such as effective multiplication factor, sodium void worth, and Doppler coefficients. The posterior mean R^* , corresponding to the most probable value of a variable of interest, and the posterior uncertainty ΔR^* after assimilation, are estimated by substituting x^* and D_x^* into Eq. (6) and Eq. (1), respectively, leading to

$$\begin{aligned} R^* &= R_0 + S_R (x^* - x_0), \\ \Delta R_R^* &= \sqrt{S_R^\top D_x^* S_R}, \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

where S_R is the sensitivity of this variable with respect to nuclear data variations. In the LFR context, assimilation allows the generation of project-specific adjusted libraries with improved predictive power. The adjusted covariance matrices also provide a refined basis for future uncertainty propagation studies and safety analyses.

3.5. Lessons learnt from the Integral Data Assimilation for the ASTRID core

The integral data used in the assimilation work of JEFF-3.1.1 conducted in 2017 led to the reassessment of nuclear data of interest for the study of the ASTRID core [13]. Revisions proposed for the nuclear data of isotopes U-238, Pu-239, Pu-240, Pu-242 were found to significantly affect the neutronic characteristics of the core. Furthermore, the reassessment of the fission and the capture cross sections of minor actinides had a non-negligible impact on the radiological characteristics of spent fuel assemblies, such as activity and decay heat. The propagated bias $R^* - R_0$ (i.e. the correction made by Integral Data Assimilation) on the ASTRID reactivity at Beginning of Cycle was -391 pcm. Moreover, the associated nuclear data uncertainty was significantly reduced, from an initial value of $\Delta R_R = 1558$ pcm to $\Delta R_R^* = 470$ pcm, following assimilation. These results demonstrated the effectiveness of integral data assimilation in reducing the uncertainties associated with nuclear data, thanks to the relatively small experimental uncertainties of criticality measurements. As for the total sodium void effect, the propagated bias was found to be small due to compensating effects between the nuclear data of different heavy metals. Nevertheless, the associated uncertainty was reduced from 23 cents down to 11 cents. Also, the integral data assimilation process enabled to identify the erroneous nuclear data evaluation of Na-23 in JEFF-3.1.1 which was replaced with the Na-23 nuclear data from JEFF-3.2. The propagated biases on the Doppler effect and the control rods weight were 1.1% and 1.5%, respectively. Integral data assimilation halved the uncertainty of both variables. The main advantages of reducing the uncertainties associated with the Doppler effect, the sodium void effect and the weight of the control rods is that it allows to reduce the safety margins associated with accidental scenarios. Reference [14] discussed the benefits of integral data assimilation on design studies of the ASTRID cores. Notably, this resulted in a saving of 20 back up assemblies that had been planned for the first divergence of the core. Furthermore, the large uncertainties related to the ASTRID reactivity had a practical impact on fuel enrichment. The bias had to be compensated for by increasing the Pu fuel enrichment by 0.32%, to meet the fuel cycle constraint at core equilibrium. Integral data assimilation performed in 2017 demonstrated the advantages of this methodology. Similar benefits are expected when this approach will be applied to the *newcleo* cores.

4. CONCLUSIONS AND PERSPECTIVES

The V&V Neutronics Plan for LFR-AS-30 and LFR-AS-200 establishes a robust, traceable, and standard-compliant framework for the qualification of neutronic codes. It demonstrates the feasibility of using existing fast reactor experimental databases, supplemented by lead-reflected benchmarks, to validate the computational methods employed in LFR design and safety studies. The integration of uncertainty quantification and data assimilation represents a modern scientific approach aligned with international best practices. Future activities will focus on expanding the database of lead-cooled experiments, refining cross-section evaluations for lead isotopes and establishing automated data assimilation pipelines. These efforts enhance confidence in accuracy of neutronic predictions for *newcleo*'s LFR designs and support the licensing process.

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